

NAVIGATING CHALLENGES: A CASE STUDY ON ISSUES IN IMPLEMENTING RESULTS-BASED PERFORMANCE IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OF TACLOBAN CITY

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Navigating Challenges: A Case Study on Issues in Implementing Results-Based Performance in the Schools Division of Tacloban City

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Abstract

The study was conducted to determine the issues and challenges of RPMS implementation in public schools in Tacloban City Division. The study utilized qualitative case study design and was participated by seven secondary level public school Master Teachers. A researcher-made guide questions were used to interview participants. The data were analyzed using thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke (2012). The study found eleven themes that present the issues and challenges experienced by the teachers in the RPMS implementation. The themes also include the identified recommendation of master teachers to improve RPMS. For the issues that teachers face in relation to RPMS implementation, the study identified low-level RPMS appreciation, lack of technical assistance, more of a burden to teachers increased workload, and ineffective in measuring teacher's overall performance. As for the challenges, the study identified completing RPMS tools with limited time, heavy teaching workloads and ancillary tasks, understanding the concept of RPMS and its indicators, rating teachers and their attitudes and perception towards RPMS, and antagonistic environment due to RPMS. For the improvement of RPMS implementation, the study recommended to make RPMS more teacher-friendly, make RPMS easier to comply, and reorientation and technical assistance. The study concluded that there are indeed issues and challenges in RPMS implementation that requires attention for improvement.

Keywords: *Results-Based Performance Management System, challenges experienced, teaching workloads and ancillary tasks, attitudes and perception towards RPMS*

Introduction

Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS) is an organization-wide assessment tool the Department of Education (DepEd) provides. It is utilized by public school teachers in the Philippines to ensure the quality of teacher performance at the different stages of their career levels (Mercado, 2020). DepEd first introduced RPMS in 2015 but started its full implementation in the school year 2018-2019. The RPMS tool, as provided by DepEd Memorandum No. 008, s. 2023 follows a cycle for teachers, including Performance Planning and Commitment for Cycle I, Cycle II involves Performance Monitoring and Coaching, Cycle III conducts Performance and Evaluation, and Cycle IV involves Performance Rewarding and Development Planning (Department of Education, 2023).

Using the RPMS tools, master teachers, head teachers, or school heads monitor teachers' performances. The tools require various means of verification (MOVs), which are hard evidence that teachers use to prove the attainment of its 37 strands or objectives alongside indicators that rate performance from outstanding to poor (Department of Education, 2018).

Recent events and studies, however, believe this claim of optimizing performance. Lacayanga (2019) conducted a study on the problems encountered by teachers during RPMS implementation. The researcher surveyed ninety-four public school teachers who also served as study participants. According to the participants, the RPMS rating tool was extra challenging because of the hurdles in accomplishing the necessary outputs for every objective, which they do on top of their regular teaching tasks.

The Philippine Institute for Development Studies supports this sentiment in a policy brief, which declared that the actual teaching work of teachers is being sidelined by non-teaching tasks (PIDS, 2019). While the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers mandates that teachers devote a maximum of six hours of classroom per day, additional administrative or support roles are assigned to them, eroding the quality of their teaching.

Education experts like Dr. Ed Fermin of the National Teachers College also think that teachers in the Philippines are overworked, exacerbating learning poverty. Lessening or eliminating teachers' administrative functions would jumpstart the system and stop the further decline of primary education in the Philippines, allowing teachers to focus on learning delivery and spend more time with learners (Magsambol, 2022).

Despite the prominence of RPMS in the Philippine education system, more studies need to be investigating the issues and challenges teachers face about its implementation, particularly in the Tacloban City Division. As early as 2018, DepEd already recognized that there are points for improvement in the RPMS implementation, and it has requested teachers to help identify related issues and problems and to participate in crafting solutions and ways forward (DepEd, 2018). However, to date, its implementation has not yet been fully explored by scholars and educators.

Considering all these issues, this study investigates the experiences, challenges, and issues of public-school teachers in the Tacloban City Division regarding the implementation of RPMS. Tacloban is a highly urbanized city with schools located both in rural

communities in the peripheries and within the city proper. Doing the study in Tacloban City Division is significant if it wants to capture the issues related to RPMS regardless of the school setting and location.

Challenges in this study are specific difficulties, obstacles, or problems that individuals or groups face within a particular context. Issues differ from challenges in that they are more encompassing and often involve broader contexts, while challenges are more specific difficulties that require focused problem-solving. There may be other factors contributing to the burdens of teachers, but this study is limited to the burdens related to RPMS as perceived and narrated by the teachers themselves.

The study will also find out if compliance with RPMS competes with teachers' time for teaching since this might impact students' performance, especially in standard literacy and numeracy tests. The recent performance of Tacloban City students in the tests could be more satisfactory. In the 2021 English Literacy Assessment, for example, only forty-three (43%) of one thousand nine hundred eighteen (1,918) students who were assessed passed as independent readers; the rest were classified either as functional or frustration readers. In the numeracy tests, sixty-three percent (63%) of the two thousand five hundred thirty-five (2,535) students assessed were classified as non-numerates.

However, in the years before this assessment, in 2019, it was one hundred percent (100%). In 2021, ninety-eight percent (98%) of schools in Tacloban City were ranked "best" in the delivery units, meaning they fared well on the results of the RPMS evaluation, which is the basis of the ranking. Teachers of these schools received sixty-five percent (65%) of their monthly salary for the top-up performance-based bonuses (PBB).

As it is, there is a dissonance between students' performance in standard literacy and numeracy tests and the purported performance of teachers based on the RPMS evaluation. This dissonance suggests inaccuracy in the RPMS implementation and the non-readiness of students in measuring up to standards, which could be attributed to teacher factors. Hence, this study must be conducted to generate the views and experiences of teachers on the RPMS and how it affects their work in the classroom, which prepares students for literacy and numeracy assessments.

This study explores and describes teachers' direct experiences with RPMS through their own words and narration. It uses the qualitative method, which is the more appropriate approach when one wants to know details and generate fresh insights on a subject. The data generated from the study will come in the form of words and not numbers (Punch, K. F, 2013).

Overall, this study's results will concretize or deflate other studies' findings regarding RPMS implementation. It will also propose solutions to evaluate teachers' performance in a manner that is accurate and not burdensome to teachers.

Research Questions

This study explored the issues and challenges experienced by public elementary and high school teachers in the Tacloban City Division in relation to Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) implementation. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What issues do teachers in Tacloban City face in the implementation of RPMS?
2. What challenges do teachers in Tacloban City face in the implementation of RPMS?
3. How may the RPMS implementation be improved?

Literature Review

DepEd Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS)

Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS) being implemented among elementary and secondary public-school teachers through Department Order No. 2, S.2015, or the guidelines on establishing and implementing the Results-based Performance Management System in the Department of Education (Department of Education, 2015). The implementation of RPMS was further strengthened and clarified with the release of DepEd Memorandum no. 008, s. 2023, which provides the multi-year guidelines for RPMS implementation among professional teachers (Department of Education, 2023).

RPMS follows four (4) cycles. Cycle 1 is done a week before the opening of classes. The activity in this phase includes a discussion of the RPMS tools. After the discussion, they are expected to develop a development plan based on the result of the teacher's self-assessment tool (SAT) and signed Individual Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). Cycle II involves Performance Monitoring and Coaching. Once performance targets are set, master teachers or assigned raters should regularly track the progress of employees' performance against their agreed targets. The activity is prescribed to determine the progress in achieving the objectives.

During the review, the rater shall inform the Ratee of his or her performance status. Coaching, feedback, and appropriate interventions shall be provided whenever necessary. The outputs are the agreements based on IPCRF and Development Plans. Cycle III conducts Performance and Evaluation.

The activity for this phase is year-end review and assessment, portfolio evaluation, or the collection of the evidence of accomplishments and computation of final rating.

The timeline is set a week after graduation. The tools and forms needed are the RPMS Tools, IPCRF, SAT, and IPCRF-Development Plans using Performance Monitoring & Coaching Form (PMCF), and the output is IPCRF with Computed Final Rating. The rating uses the rubrics provided in the RPMS tool, ranging from outstanding to poor performances. Cycle IV involves Performance Rewarding and Development Planning. This final phase focuses on recognizing and rewarding employees for their performance. The rater shall discuss and provide qualitative comments, observations, and recommendations on the rates of performance commitment, competency assessment, and significant incidents, which shall be used for training and professional development. The rater and the rate shall discuss ways forward based on the performance of the rate for the school year (Pangilinan, 2019).

Performance management systems are a crucial aspect of organizational management, aiming to measure and improve the performance of individuals, teams, and the organization (Awan et al., 2020). Conceptual literature provides insights into the design, implementation, and effectiveness of performance management systems. These studies emphasize the importance of aligning performance management systems with strategic goals, effectively managing dissent, promoting quality, and ensuring efficient process management.

Furthermore, performance management has been a hot topic among teachers in the Philippines since its conception and implementation (Torero & Mojica, 2021). Awan, Habib, Akhtar, and Naveed (2020) claimed that several initiatives have been conducted to achieve a balanced performance measurement system.

However, more must be done to guide the implementers in introducing PMS to its users. This statement was agreed upon by Brown, O'Kane, Mazumdar, and McCracken (2018). However, the group emphasized that most performance management is more process-driven and is more concerned with performance appraisal (PA) instead of investigating PMS holistically. A good PMS can encourage and align employees with the organization's goals (Siraj & Hågen, 2023). Brown (2018) and his group suggested more research that investigates the gaps in the system to manage employees effectively in the future.

Challenges and Issues in the Implementation of RPMS

In the comparative analysis study of Cakir and Adiguzel (2020), they argued that organizations need help implementing performance management systems as some aspects are not considered. The study data was collected from 50 employees using Cronbach Alpha (0.935). The results show that the success of any system implemented in an organization largely depends on the commitment of top-level management, and all levels of the organization must be adequately trained on how PMS should be conducted. The study also emphasized the importance of role definition in preventing conflict in the organization. The study recommended open communication in the organization to encourage its members to discuss their problems and opportunities with their supervisors.

Thusi (2023) claimed that PMS needs to be revised because discussions about performance management are centered on goal setting and only happen during evaluations and formal reviews. Employees and managers dread these formal reviews due to biases, leniency, and relationship management (LaBat, 2018).

Modipane, Botha, and Blom (2018) researched to measure the provincial government department's employees' perceived effectiveness of PMS in South Africa. The study was conducted on the assumption that employees' experience of PMS may differ from what it was intended for. The quantitative research was conducted on 247 employees, with their PMS impression measured based on the tool's accuracy and fairness. The study found that the employees view PMS as deficient in coaching from the management and non-compliance with procedural, distributive, and procedural justice principles. They also view PMS as unfair. However, employees perceived PMS as accurate and were generally satisfied with the system's implementation.

Monroe-Wise et. al (2019) suggested that scorecard projects can fail because of poor technical know-how and knowledge among implementers about how PMS works, defects in the system, organizational challenges, lack of employee engagement, and poor communication and leadership issues during the implementation phase.

Kaupa and Atiku (2020), in their study on the implementation challenges of performance management systems in the Namibian Public Sector, found that the primary issue of PMS in the public sector is a lack of training and proper orientation among its users, added lack of supporting policies on the implementation process of the system, inadequate monitoring and evaluation scheme, poor communication in planning and implementation, poor feedback mechanism, and lack of employee involvement on the implementation of PMS. The qualitative study utilized the data gathered from 42 participants. The data was analyzed using thematic data analysis, where core topics emerging from the interviews and discussions were grouped and analyzed. The study recommended that the management provide training and capacity building to educate the employees on the goals and benefits of PMS and enforce policies for the system's compliance.

Alshaikhi and Alshaikhi (2021) similarly studied the Saudi Ministry of Education case, specifically on the effectiveness of PMS on teachers, including the system's shortcomings, to identify ways to improve and develop the teaching quality of educators in Saudi Arabia. A survey was conducted among 502 teachers. The data was analyzed using the statistical package of social science (SPSS). Based on the study results, teachers' perception of PMS was more inclined to dissatisfaction.

This perception emanates from the problems encountered in the performance management process. The participants also shared that the system needs to represent the necessary information to help managers make informed decisions and policies about the teachers. Other issues identified in the study were the lack of training for head teachers to enable them to conduct PMS effectively and the

teachers' beliefs that there are bias errors in PMS implementation due to teachers' dissatisfaction. The study recommended resolving the system's shortcomings and improving the teachers' satisfaction with PMS.

A scoping review by Vuong and Nguyen (2022) identified 31 factors contributing to PMS implementation failure. The study suggested several parameters that need to be considered for the success of performance management system implementation. Some of the identified problems of PMS implementation were low priority on the implementation, insufficient resources and capacity available for the implementation, requiring more time and effort than expected, organizational members lack a positive attitude towards PMS, lack of knowledge and skill regarding the PMS, too many KPIs defined, the organizations measures the wrong KPIs, resistance from organizational members towards PMS, lack of performance management culture, insufficient link between the PMS and the reward system. The study also found that PMS is not used for the organization's daily management, while some participants do not see any value in the PMS.

Arumugham, Maelah, and Aman (2018) attempted to explain the challenges encountered during PMS implementation in a Government Linked Company (GLC). The study used an explanatory case study method, while data collection was conducted through semi-structured interviews, direct observations, document reviews, and informal conversations. The study found that some of the challenges in implementing PMS include employee readiness, PMS objectives and direction, PMS measurements, and commitment from the management. The study recommended a control system to improve the implementation of PMS in the organization.

The study's findings above were supported by Khumhome (2019), who found that individual goal ambiguity is one factor affecting the success of PMS implementation. Aside from that, the study observed that PMS is bound to fail when performance indicators are not clear, and performance appraisal needs to be more accurate when there is discontinuous work performance monitoring. Performance appraisal is not linked to performance improvement and reward. The study suggested that top management commitment, skills, attitude, and knowledge of the manager, positive perception of PMS by the employees, employee involvement, and organizational culture contribute to the effectiveness of a PMS.

To determine the issues and concerns of teachers on RPMS, Ormilla (2021) surveyed 94 public school teachers who also served as the study participants. The teachers were asked to identify key result areas (KRA) of RPMS on a scale of 1-15, where 5- very difficult, 4- moderately difficult, 3- fair, 2- moderately easy, and 1- very easy. Based on the results, the participants identified Curriculum and Planning as very difficult KRA, Content Knowledge and Pedagogy as moderately tricky, Learning Environment and Diversity of learners were identified as fair, and Assessment and Reporting were moderately easy. In contrast, the Plus Factor was identified as very easy. According to the participants, the RPMS rating tool was extra challenging because there were many hurdles in accomplishing and meeting the necessary outputs for every objective and daily task. The study recommended equipping the teachers with the necessary skills to accomplish satisfactory KRAs, particularly in Curriculum Planning and Content and Pedagogy.

Torneo and Mojica (2019) claimed that the performance management process in the Philippines is bureaucratic and highly administrative, a mere burden for employees and managers. Thus, the researchers recommended that the performance management system be changed to improve employee motivation and help employees achieve organizational goals.

How to Improve the Performance Management System

Apart from determining the challenges encountered by teachers and organizations in implementing performance management systems, some studies explored how these performance management systems can be improved. Singh (2020) reviews the effectiveness of quality management systems, notably ISO 9000, in improving organizational performance. They emphasize the importance of the ISO 9000 standards in promoting quality management and continuous improvement. This literature highlights the role of quality management systems in enhancing organizational effectiveness and efficiency.

A study that aimed to examine the performance management systems and the characteristics that predict desirable organizational outcomes found that the four most desirable attributes of PMS are those that focus on the achievements of employees. The PMS should also evaluate employees' contextual performance, facilitate the construction of individual development plans for employees, and allow participative decision-making between managers and subordinates (Owolabi & Adeosun, 2021). The study utilized the survey results of 159 participants from the College of Business at San Jose University. The study recommended that organizations implement the identified characteristics into PMS to improve the system's perceived effectiveness and increase employee engagement.

A descriptive cross-sectional study on the influence of the performance management system on employee productivity in Kiambu County found that feedback and reward were the strongest predictors of employee productivity (Owino et al., 2019). For PMS to succeed, there should be realistic and clear goals for the team, regular review discussions on the employees' performance, regular constructive feedback, and a reward system linked to the appraisal results, which should be just and fair.

Jugmohun (2018) argued that while adopting a PMS is essential, management should also be aware of the number of factors that make a PMS work. Some factors cited by the study include training, a balanced scorecard, employee engagement, top management commitment, reward management, the culture and behavior of the organization's members, and enterprise resource planning.

In another study, the research focused on the managers and supervisors and their experiences with PMS implementation instead of looking at the employees. The study's data was obtained through in-depth interviews, reflective engagements, and observations with

managers and supervisors. The study found that a range of factors influence the implementation of PMS, and the success of PMS depends on the extent of management skills. Thus, managers should be developed for them to have the ability to manage in transforming a complex environment, and they should be designed to be effective in planning, coordination, and monitoring soft skills where communication and collaboration can be focused (Nxumalo et al., 2018).

A specific study that explored the level of implementation of RPMS in the Philippines was conducted by Dizon (2018) and the company. The study evaluated the implementation level of the RPMS tool on the teachers and non-teaching employees of the Department of Education in Gapan City using the Control Theory of Performance Management System. The tool used measured the following for the study: performance planning and commitment, performance monitoring and coaching, performance review and evaluation, and performance rewards and development planning. The study found the need for periodic evaluation to update the implementation of RPMS and the need for strict implementation of RPMS Guidelines.

Moreover, Keeton (2018) proposes a theory for improved strategic leadership, focusing on command, leadership, intelligence, and management (CLIM). This theoretical perspective draws on principles grounded within the military and aims to introduce the concept of intelligence as a critical element of strategic leadership.

This literature emphasizes the importance of effective leadership in driving organizational performance. Studies show that such feedback processes as appraisal and evaluation should be optional for improving performance and employee satisfaction. In the work of Pulakos (2019), it was stated that daily interactions and open and timely feedback help the employee to correct mistakes and enhance achievements and energetic levels. Also, constant feedback helps to avoid sharing information only when something is wrong or has gone bad, creating an atmosphere of accessible communication and increasing trust between subordinates and superiors. Furthermore, another study by Pervaiz, Li, and He (2021) emphasized that appreciable roles of employee participation in goal formulation are very effective in improving staff commitment and performance results.

Similarly, the research study of Liu and Liu (2022) stated the benefits of recognition and rewards as a way of encouraging the morale and performance of employees. According to Hussain (2019), when the recognition has to be given at the right time and with the correct values, it helps to maintain the cultural benchmarks of appreciation, accomplishment, and high-performance security. Hence, it was recommended that rewards should be personalized and suited to the choice of the individuals in question to optimize the benefits of the systems.

Another aspect of performance management is the implementation of sophisticated software solutions that help optimize the process, increase coordination, and offer valuable data. The current PMS tools utilized at the Department of Education are manual, which takes time to accomplish. The digitized PMS should include real-time feedback, performance tracking, and more data set plans that help decision-makers (Sahlin et al., 2019). These tools can also help perform remote management, which is specifically helpful for blended and remote learning environments (Moorhouse & Wong, 2022).

Another recommendation for effective PMS is using coaching and mentoring, as they are perceived as powerful tools that support individuals in continuously gaining from development and performance enhancement. As Peláez, Salanova, and Martinez (2020) considered, the difference between coaching and mentoring is that coaching gives employees particular skills and helps them achieve personal objectives in the organization, whereas mentoring serves long-term career management. The two models promote the employer's culture and support the employees in sharing their knowledge, improving organizational effectiveness.

In addition, Zhejiang (2022) argued that positive criticism that directs more on what exactly was done right could influence positive behavior change among employees through motivation. Furthermore, Sales (2019) emphasized that performance reviews should focus on the future and the employees' development potential instead of looking at the past and criticizing mistakes. By developing an employee as the organization's goal, the objectives of both the supervisor and the organization will be achieved (Mohammad, 2018).

Likewise, Ormilla (2021) conducted a similar study inquiring about the status of the implementation of RPMS in Ifugao public elementary schools. The quantitative research had 466 study participants who responded to the survey questionnaire. The study revealed that the RPMS tool was highly implemented in the Schools Division of Ifugao. However, their results were similar to those of Dizon (2018), where strict and consistent compliance with RPMS Guidelines was recommended to ensure the teachers' performance is assessed adequately with bias. The study also recommended shared responsibility between the rater and the ratee in monitoring and tracking relevant events related to RPMS. Feedback and mentoring should also be provided to enhance the work and behavior of teachers.

A study in Laoag by Abun (2021) has opined that such variations of feedback impact the employee's capability to fully utilize his strength base and consequently on performance, which improves when confidence is heightened. These approaches appeal to the positive psychology framework and advocate for employees' general welfare and happiness.

Given the above literature, the study is unique and different from previous studies cited because the previous studies did not zero in on the specific issues and challenges experienced by teachers, particularly the heavy paperwork related to RPMS implementation in the country. Hence, it is different from what has been done in the past. Therefore, the study is not a duplication of other studies done in previous years.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a Case Study qualitative research approach to achieve its objectives, as the proponent was interested in gathering non-numerical information through audio-recording discussions and in-depth interviews related to teachers' issues and challenges in implementing RPMS.

Specifically, the study used case studies to achieve its objectives. Creswell (2014) describes a case study as a "qualitative design in which the researcher explores in depth a program, event, activity, process, or one or more individuals" (p.241). The data of a case study comes from archival records, documentation, direct observations, interviews, physical artifacts, and participant observations (Yin, 1994). A case study is chosen as a design for this study as it is aligned with the goals of this research, which are to gain a concrete understanding and to describe the experiences of public-school teachers as they comply with RPMS. A case study explores the meaning, characteristics, and implications of the phenomenon being investigated.

Respondents

The study invited seven Master Teachers (MT) from the different schools in Tacloban City Division to be its key informants. The MTs were selected and designated by the School Head to participate in the study as key informants. Thus, the participants for the key informant interviews were based on their position in schools. Only master teachers who underwent RPMS were qualified to participate in the study. Of the seven master teacher participants, two are males, and five are females. Three are single, and four are married. Out of the married participants, two of them have three or more children, while the two others only have two or fewer children.

The study employed purposive sampling to select research participants. Purposive sampling is a type of nonprobability sampling whose main objective is to produce a sample that can be assumed to be logically representative of the target population (Lavrakas, 2008). The method is often accomplished by applying expert knowledge of the target population to select a sample in a nonrandom manner that represents a cross-section of the population.

Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made interview guide as its data-gathering instrument. The instrument has three main sections and was used to obtain the necessary data and information from the seven key informant Master Teachers from the Tacloban City Division.

The first section provided preliminary information about the study introduced the researcher, obtained informed consent, and provided other critical information in accordance with the universally accepted ethical conduct of studies.

The second section was considered the primary interview. This section was designed to draw out the participants' impressions, issues, and challenges regarding the implementation of RPMS within the Department. Hence, the research instrument collected the respondents' views on RPMS, the problems and challenges they encountered during the implementation, their general impression of RPMS, and other relevant information. The research instrument also asked the participants to share their ideas on improving RPMS.

The third section of the research instrument mainly wraps up the interview by providing a summary and thanking the participants for their time.

Procedure

Data was collected through researcher-made interview guide. There were two interview protocols, particularly for administrators and teachers. The interview consisted of three main parts. Part I focuses on establishing rapport to the participants and explaining the risk and benefits of the research including the informed consent. The second part was the primary interview which was design to draw out the participants' impressions, issues, and challenges regarding the implementation of RPMS within the Department and how this can be improved. The last part was just a wrap-up of the interview.

The interview lasted more or less than thirty minutes and was conducted in their respective schools during their most convenient time. Interviews were audio/phone recorded. A post-interview was conducted for member checking to allow the participants to validate, change, and enhance their responses.

Data Analysis

This study adopted the thematic analysis framework of Braun and Clarke (2006). Thematic analysis is an approach to analyzing qualitative data to answer broad or narrow research questions about people's views, perceptions, experiences, and representations of a particular phenomenon (Brule, 2020). It should be considered a foundational method for qualitative analysis as it offers core skills for conducting several forms of qualitative analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

This paper followed the six-phase data analysis process proposed by Braun and Clarke (2012). The phases include the following:

Phase One: Familiarizing with the data. Familiarization requires reading and rereading the entire dataset or listening to a recorded audiotape to be familiar with the gathered data. In this phase, the researcher reread the transcriptions and identified necessary

information relevant to the research questions.

Phase Two: Generating initial codes. The phase starts when the researcher has become familiar with the data. Phase two entails the initial production of codes from the data. The process requires the researcher to revisit the data now and then for reference and validation (Nowell et al., 2017). Qualitative coding is a process of reflection involving interaction and thinking about the dataset (Savage, 2000). Coding enables the researcher to simplify and focus on particular data characteristics. At this phase, the researcher identified essential text sections and assigned labels to index them as they relate to a theme in the data.

Phase Three: Searching for themes. Themes are broad and involve active interpretation of the codes and the data. According to DeSantis and Ugarizza (2000), a theme is an abstract entity that takes meaning and identity to a repeated experience and its varied manifestations. Thus, a theme catches and unifies the nature or basis of the experience into a meaningful whole. In this phase, the researcher reviewed the list of codes and their associated meanings. Then, she collated the codes into broader themes that reveal exciting concepts from the data. Searching for themes is a repetitive process involving moving codes back and forth to form varied themes. In this process, not all codes fit others; others will become subthemes. Redundant codes can be temporarily placed in a mixed theme, which you can narrow down later and disregard those that do not seem to fit in any of the themes.

Phase Four: Reviewing themes. This is the phase where the researcher reviewed and refined the themes identified in phase three. The researcher also combined similar themes and split those that were not coherent. The themes were considered carefully to cover the exciting part and ensure that specific ideas were noticed.

Phase Five: Defining and naming themes. This phase involves reviewing, defining, and providing names for each theme. Braun and Clarke (2006) suggested that these names have to be catchy and should immediately give the reader an idea of what the theme is about. At this phase, the researcher considered how the themes fit into the overall research and how the data relates to the research questions. The researcher reviewed all data thoroughly, and the coding was examined at least twice.

Phase Six: Producing the report. At this stage, the researcher ensured that the report was coherent, concise, logical, non-repetitive, engaging, and straightforward. To provide rigor and validity of the argument, the researcher referred back to the literature mentioned in the study.

Ethical Considerations

This section explains the measures to ensure the study's credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability based on Lincoln and Guba's (1985) criteria of ensuring rigor. Rigor is demonstrated through the researcher's attention to and transparency of the researcher's conduct throughout the study (Streubert & Carpenter, 1995).

Credibility. This criterion was achieved by engaging with teachers willing to participate in the study and sharing their experiences related to RPMS implementation. The researcher reviewed the transcriptions thoroughly to ensure that the formulated meanings of the statements culled from the interview transcript truly reflect the participants' experiences. This ensures that their experiences' shared narratives and interpretations are accurate. The researcher explained each part of the research in which the participants were involved.

Transferability. To meet this criterion, the researcher ensures that the research findings can be utilized by other studies related to the topic and transferred to a similar platform without losing their meaning. Hence, the researcher sought the comments and suggested revisions of the panelists to ensure the reliability and credibility of its findings.

Dependability. Koch (1994) suggests regular auditing during the entire research process to ensure the study's dependability. The audit was conducted by the researcher's adviser and consultants to provide guidance and ensure that the form and context of the study were in accordance with the standards provided by the research institution.

Confirmability. Confirmability will only be accomplished when the research study provides an audit trail throughout the study (Nowell et al., 2017). The researcher conducted systematic documentation during the study to satisfy the confirmability criterion. This ensures that the findings are based on the participants' points of view and experiences and not tainted by personal biases and opinions of the researcher. The researcher employed reflexivity to ensure that the interpretation and analysis were more effective and impartial. Reflexivity involves evaluating and consciously acknowledging the preconceived notions and assumptions the researcher brings into the research that help shape the results or research outcome (Wilkie, 2015).

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the findings and explanations of the analysis, interpretations, and conclusions drawn from the study's data, particularly the issues and challenges of RPMS implementation in the Tacloban City Division.

Based on the participants' responses, eleven themes were generated describing the issues and challenges of RPMS implementation, as experienced by the teachers of Tacloban City Division. These themes include low-level RPMS appreciation, lack of technical assistance, increased workload, inability to measure teacher's overall performance, completing RPMS tools with limited time, heavy teaching workloads and ancillary tasks, understanding the concept of RPMS and its indicators, rating teachers, teachers' their attitudes and perception towards RPMS, antagonistic environment due to RPMS, make RPMS more teacher-friendly, make RPMS easier to

comply, and reorientation and technical assistance.

Issues Teachers Face in the Implementation of Results-based Performance Management System

The issues teachers face in the implementation of RPMS were derived from the participants' perspectives through the interviews. The ideas are presented in Table 1. Consequently, four themes were developed based on the case interviews.

Table 1. *Key issues teachers face in RPMS implementation*

Case 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unsure how to conduct RPMS • Tasks are not applicable • No proper and insufficient RPMS orientation • Lack of knowledge and understanding on RPMS • No technical assistance • No technical expert to consult • Completion of RPMS is for compliance only • More of a burden
Case 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of knowledge and understanding on RPMS • No proper and insufficient RPMS orientation • Completion of RPMS is for compliance only
Case 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No proper and insufficient RPMS orientation • Lack of knowledge and understanding on RPMS • Ambiguous/incomplete instructions • Completion of RPMS is for compliance only • Ineffective in measuring teacher's overall performance • Affects teacher's time for teaching
Case 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No proper and insufficient RPMS orientation • Unsure how to conduct RPMS • Ambiguous/incomplete instructions • Lack of knowledge and understanding on RPMS • Completion of RPMS is for compliance only
Case 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of knowledge and understanding on RPMS • Completion of RPMS is for compliance only • More of a burden • No proper and insufficient RPMS orientation • Ambiguous/incomplete instructions • Evaluators ask more MOVs than what is required • Late dissemination of information/changes
Case 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unsure how to conduct RPMS • No proper and insufficient RPMS orientation • Lack of knowledge and understanding on RPMS • Late dissemination of information/changes • Additional task • Completion of RPMS is for compliance only • More of a burden
Case 7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More of a burden • Unsure how to conduct RPMS • Ineffective in measuring teacher's overall performance

Some of the detailed investigations from the participants while interviewing are given below:

Case 1 shared that one of the critical issues of RPMS implementation is the uncertainty of using the tool. The problem worsens because it is hard to find help, and there is no need to consult during the implementation period. Some workers do RPMS for compliance without understanding its value as a process. Again, a good number of teachers are not sure what they should be doing while doing RPMS, especially when some exercises are seen as not applicable to them.

Case 2 pointed out that implementing the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) encounters numerous vital concerns. One is the significant need for more information about and understanding of RPMS among teachers, which affects its practical use. This problem is then escalated by inadequate and wrongly done orientation programs, so staff members cannot engage well with the system. Many teachers, therefore, perform their tasks only because they are required to do so without showing any commitment to

improving performance or growth in organizations.

Case 3 mentioned a confusing and insufficient orientation on the system, a significant problem because most teachers need a proper understanding of the system. Vague and splitting procedures are even more problematic as the staff still needs to learn about the correct RPMS approach. Consequently, almost every teacher finishes the program's set tasks mechanically, without regard them as auspicious for performance improvement. Furthermore, RPMS is not always suitable for providing a comprehensive assessment of a teacher's performance and undermines the core teaching time because of the emphasis on scores and ranking.

Case 4 perceives that some critical concerns have been realized while using the RPMS in implementing the performance management system. Firstly, there is a general weakness in RPMS orientation, where teachers need more guidance on performing RPMS. This makes it worse by having unclear and half-baked instructions, making it seem like teachers need to understand the procedures or what is expected. Moreover, there are many concerns regarding the overall knowledge and comprehension of the system among teachers who want to perform meaningful interactions with RPMS. According to Case Number 4, these issues show the need for structure, better and clearer elaboration of instructions, and communication to improve the implementation and usage of RPMS.

Case 5 perceives those numerous significant challenges have emerged in the rollout of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). One is the widespread need for familiarity and comprehension of RPMS among teachers, which impedes their ability to interact with the system effectively. Furthermore, many teachers perceive RPMS tasks as obligations for meeting compliance standards rather than recognizing them as valuable tools for enhancing performance. This perception is worsened by the belief that RPMS is more of a burden than a beneficial process. Additionally, adequate RPMS orientation and clear instructions contribute to clarity and inefficiencies in its execution. Moreover, evaluators occasionally request excessive MOVs, unnecessarily complicating and overburdening the workload. Finally, delayed communication of information or changes exacerbates these challenges, impeding the smooth integration and adoption of RPMS.

Case 6 described RPMS as unclear in terms of execution, coupled with the lack of need for more lack of proper guidance. General ignorance and misconceptions regarding RPMS further stress this lack of appropriate guidance. Also, delays or changes in information flow complicate the implementation process by confusing the teachers even more. Furthermore, delegating new tasks creates further workload on the employees, resulting in RPMS completion as a mere compliance. As a result, RPMS is seen as a process that imposes rather than provides value for teachers.

Case 7 shared that the teachers regard RPMS as a strain rather than a helpful process, which might influence their keenness to utilize it optimally. Also, with multiple hospital staff, there needs to be clarity on the best practices to adopt when implementing RPMS; hence, this takes a lot of time to implement. In addition, RPMS is seen to fail to provide a fair assessment of teachers' performance, thus contributing to the questionable viability of RPMS as an assessment tool. Solving these problems entails increased training and much better strategies and guidelines that, if necessary, call into question the approach taken to teacher performance evaluation within the framework of RPMS.

Moreover, the following themes were obtained from the cases:

Low-level Results-based Performance Management System appreciation

A level of RPMS appreciation refers to a deeper understanding of the participants and the rationale behind RPMS. Appreciation means they understand why RPMS is implemented and, more importantly, know how to conduct and accomplish its tools. However, based on the data gathered, some of the participants indicated that they needed help with how to conduct RPMS and were not sure of the system's purpose. Some expressed that they do not see the value of RPMS, while others admitted that they lack knowledge and understanding of RPMS.

The teachers' low appreciation for RPMS coincides with the study of Awan, Habib, Akhtar, and Naveed (2020), which claimed that several studies have been conducted to achieve a balanced performance measurement system, yet little has been done to guide the implementers on how to introduce PMS to its users.

The low appreciation of teachers on RPMS also stems from the teachers' claims that the mode of verification (MOVs) does not apply to their students or classroom setting or that the instructions on how to complete the tools needed to be clarified. For instance, one of the KRAs of RPMS alludes to indigenous peoples' education (IPed). However, not all classrooms have IP learners, and the lack of a rate for this affects the entire teacher rating. This contributes to the teachers' confusion, frustration, and further unappreciation of RPMS.

Lack of Technical Assistance

The interviews and discussions presented the numerous issues related to the implementation of RPMS. One of the issues identified was the need for more technical assistance to implement teachers, which was caused by inadequate planning, insufficient resources, lack of stakeholder engagement, unclear objectives, ineffective communication, resistance to change, and external factors beyond the control of the implementing organization. When implementation becomes problematic, it can result in delays, cost overruns, suboptimal outcomes, or even program failure. Therefore, it is essential to identify and address the underlying causes of problematic implementation as early as possible and take appropriate corrective actions to mitigate the negative impact on the project's success.

Based on the data obtained, the problematic implementation of RPMS emanates from a lack of technical assistance, which causes internal conflict or misunderstanding among teachers and between teachers and their superiors or raters. This result is similar to the findings of Modipane, Botha, and Bloom (2018), wherein they found that in their study, employees view PMS as deficient in coaching from the management and non-compliant with procedural, distributive, and procedural justice principles. In the present study, the participants shared that there was no proper RPMS orientation, and the orientation was conducted once. Hence, more is needed for them to understand and appreciate RPMS. In addition, teachers claim they need a technical expert to consult on matters they find confounding. Information is also disseminated late whenever there are changes, resulting in them cramming or needing clarification about what to do. Some participants shared that since there is no technical assistance and no technical expert they can consult, they resort to YouTube and other social media sites for ideas on how to respond to the tools.

The result is the findings of the study by Cakir and Adiguzel (2020). According to the survey, organizations have difficulty implementing performance management systems as some aspects are not considered. Further, the success of any system implemented in an organization largely depends on the commitment of top-level management, and all levels of the organization must be adequately trained on how PMS should be conducted.

Increased Workload

Most of the participants shared how they are burdened with RPMS. The burden they referred to means that a specific task, responsibility, or situation is causing an increased workload, stress, or difficulty for teachers. It implies that teachers are already dealing with a significant amount of duties and demands on their time and energy, and this additional burden is making their job more challenging. With RPMS, teachers must take on additional administrative tasks that are time-consuming and detract from their core teaching responsibilities.

The theme "increased workload" suggests that teachers were already dealing with a particular difficulty or challenge, and RPMS adds to their workload and stress levels. It highlights the need to support teachers and reduce their burden so that they can effectively fulfill their role in educating and helping students.

Based on the interviews and discussions, RPMS affects their time for teaching, and instead of doing their teaching tasks, they would ask their learners to do desk work as they need to answer the tools. Since they can no longer focus on teaching, the quality of learning is affected, and the learning competencies of learners are sacrificed. For the teachers, RPMS is an additional workload and a waste of resources as they need to present hard copies of MOVs and the tools. They must print and photocopy bulk documents, which is a waste of resources, considering the limited bond paper and other materials issued to them per school year. Since there are limited resource materials, such as paper and ink for printing, they have no choice but to spend their money, which is further detrimental to them as limited funds cause further stress. According to the teachers, instead of resting during holidays or weekends and spending time teaching learners, they are bound to complete RPMS, which is a waste of time and resources and more of a burden than a help.

These findings corroborate the findings of Noronha, Aquinas, and Menezes (2016), wherein the scoping review found low priority on the implementation, insufficient resources and capacity available for the implementation, more time and effort than expected, organizational members lack a positive attitude towards PMS, lack of knowledge and skill regarding the PMS, too many KPIs defined; the organizations measures the wrong KPIs, resistance from organizational members towards PMS, lack of performance management culture, insufficient link between the PMS and the reward system as some of the issues encountered by the participants. The study also found that PMS is not used for the organization's daily management, while some participants need to see value in the PMS.

Ineffective in measuring teacher's overall performance

Another issue that floated during the interviews and focus group discussions was the claim of the participants that RPMS is ineffective in terms of measuring or determining the overall performance of teachers, more so because some of the participants consider the submission of RPMS as mere compliance and not indeed to gauge their performance. An evaluation tool, such as the RPMS, is ineffective in measuring a teacher's overall performance if the system produces accurate and meaningful results that reflect the teacher's effectiveness in helping students learn and develop.

An ineffective measurement system may rely on narrow or limited criteria, such as modes of verification, to evaluate a teacher's performance without taking into account other important aspects of teaching, such as classroom management, student engagement, workload, creativity in lesson planning, and other relevant factors. Alternatively, an ineffective measurement system may use subjective evaluations or rely on inconsistent or biased data sources, leading to unreliable results that do not accurately reflect a teacher's overall performance.

An ineffective measurement system can create problems for teachers, students, and schools, as it may lead to unfair evaluations, demoralize teachers, and fail to identify areas for improvement.

In this study, the participants shared that they would copy their colleagues' answers since they have other tasks to do, and completing RPMS is not a priority for them compared to actual teaching or the learners' needs. In the study of Jugmohun (2018), the author emphasized that for a PMS to work, the system should be aware of the number of factors that make a PMS work. Some factors cited by the study include training, a balanced scorecard, employee engagement, top management commitment, reward management, culture

and behavior of the organization's members, and enterprise resource planning. Only through critical considerations of varying factors shall an organization effectively measure the teachers' overall performance.

Teachers' Challenges in the Implementation of Results-based Performance Management System

This section discusses the challenges teachers face regarding the implementation of RPMS. The discussion around this section presents teachers' difficulties as they respond to the RPMS requirements. The study identified four themes under this section: completing RPMS tools with limited time, understanding the concept of RPMS and its indicators, rating teachers, teachers' attitudes and perception towards RPMS, and antagonistic environment due to RPMS. The ideas of the participants are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Teachers' challenges in the implementation of RPMS

Case 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Takes time to complete RPMS • Forgets about MOV due to numerous tasks • Lacks time to document activities • Requires constant documentation • Physically tasking to complete MOVs
Case 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physically tasking to complete MOVs • Tasks are tedious • Requires excessive resources to complete MOVs • Teachers' attitudes and perception of teachers towards RPMS • Takes time to complete RPMS • How to balance professional and personal life • Lack of knowledge and understanding on RPMS • Quality of MOVs submitted • Attitudes and perception of teachers towards RPMS • No feedback mechanism
Case 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers cram to submit MOVs • How to conduct RPMS • How to secure MOVs • Lacks time to fulfill RPMS • Spends personal money for MOVs • Affects personal time • So many required MOVs • How to manage time for teaching when there are too many tasks • Insufficient materials and supplies • Submission/completion of MOVs • Cannot rate accordingly due to mandates of giving high ratings • Teachers' attitudes and perception towards RPMS
Case 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RPMS becomes a leverage of School Head/Principal against teachers • Uncertain if SH/MTs are doing RPMS correctly • SH and MTs lack knowledge on RPMS • SH/MT cannot do anything if the teacher do not have MOV
Case 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of RPMS understanding due to numerous tasks of teachers • Teachers' attitudes and perception towards RPMS • Teachers cram to submit MOVs • Evaluators/raters are overly meticulous • Submission/completion of MOVs • Physically tasking to complete MOVs
Case 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tasks are tedious • Raters tend to compromise in order for the teachers to complete the requirements • Difficulty in completing requirements due to numerous tasks • Quality of MOVs • Difficulty in rating teachers
Case 7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires constant documentation • Difficulty in completing requirements due to numerous tasks • Takes time to complete RPMS • Teachers cram to submit MOVs

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- How to manage time for teaching when there are too many tasks
 - To understand the indicators more
 - Lack of RPMS understanding
-

The details of the cases are as follows:

Case 1 believes that teachers face several challenges with the rollout of RPMS. For instance, accomplishing RPMS tasks takes time and adds stress to their tight timetables. Due to numerous tasks performed, teachers sometimes need to meet specific requirements for Mode of Verification (MOV), and certain elements may remain unrecorded. Furthermore, the continuous need for documentation makes it difficult for educators to have enough time to document their work and accomplishments properly. This need for regular documentation creates more work for them and is physically demanding, especially when filling out MOVs. Altogether, these issues show various complex issues teachers encounter in managing the RPMS implementation process.

Case 2 shared that MOVs are physically exhausting and often monotonous to execute; they require ample resources and time, which puts pressure on their already heavy workload. Due to the impossibility of combining personal and professional life, teachers need help with such a time-consuming RPMS process. Also, the revised schedule, limited familiarity with RPMS, and varying quality of MOVs suggest that many educators need to learn more about RPMS. Teachers' overall attitudes and perceptions towards RPMS are generally negative, regarding RPMS as a chore, which does not assist in improving performance. This is made worse because no feedback mechanism would help the teachers know where and how to correct their submissions or the process.

Case 3 mentions that some teachers rush to file their required Mode of Verification (MOVs) because of the limited time for RPMS and inadequate knowledge of how to undertake RPMS effectively. Personal money is sometimes used to secure MOVs, which implies losing personal time. The numerous required MOVs and inadequate materials and supplies make the process even more challenging. According to Case 3, teachers have a lot on their plate and need more time for teaching besides all these other tasks, which makes them stressed and less efficient. The submission and completion of the MOVs are very hurried, and teachers can only assess their performance if they are forced to give high scores.

Case 4 admitted that sometimes she thinks that RPMS turns into a weapon that the School Head or MT uses against teachers instead of being a tool for cooperation. Teachers are also unsure if School Heads and Master Teachers perform RPMS properly since these leaders may not fully understand the system. Moreover, if a teacher does not submit the MOV, School Heads and Master Teachers cannot do anything to address the issues, which worsens the current situation.

Case 5 explained that since they have a lot of other responsibilities, they are more likely to have negative feelings or perceptions towards RPMS due to their little understanding of the system. Teachers often scramble to meet the deadline when submitting Modes of Verification (MOVs), which is made worse by stringent and nitpicky evaluators. Case 5 also shared that the submission and completion of these MOVs are both tedious and physically wrenching, hence adding to their stress. According to Case 5, these factors explain why the uptake and use of RPMS are less successful than expected. It needs more support, clear guidelines, and efficient and burdensome processes that only add to teachers' already heavy work workload.

Case 6 pointed out that the activities involved in accomplishing RPMS are time-consuming, making it difficult for them to fulfill the requirements, among many other things they are supposed to do. This workload affects the quality of the MOVs produced since teachers cannot devote their time to meet the required standard of the MOVs as they are also involved in their core teaching functions. On the same note, raters make the process even more challenging. Furthermore, due to these challenges, it can become difficult to rate teachers reasonably and efficiently, which weakens the functionality of the RPMS.

Case 7 shared that the system demands regular documentation and recording of student progress, which cannot be fully accomplished because there are so many other demands on teachers' time. Case 7 said that RPMS is time-consuming and often results in teachers struggling to produce their MOVs on time. In addition, understanding the RPMS indicators and the struggle to manage teaching responsibilities makes teaching and RPMS challenging. Also, the process is complicated because most teachers do not know how to meet the requirements.

The following themes were generated based on the significant statements from the case.

Completing RPMS tools with limited time, heavy teaching workload and ancillary tasks

One of the main issues identified with RPMS implementation is completing the RPMS tools with limited time and other equally important tasks, such as teaching and performing ancillary tasks. Completing RPMS tools with limited time, heavy teaching workload, and ancillary tasks refers to the challenges and difficulties faced by teachers when they are required to complete performance evaluation tools as part of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) while also dealing with a heavy teaching workload and other administrative or ancillary tasks.

The RPMS is a system schools and educational institutions use to assess teachers' performance based on specific indicators, including teaching effectiveness, professional development, and contributions to the school community. Completing RPMS tools involves gathering and organizing data, documenting evidence, and reflecting on one's performance, which can be time-consuming and require

additional effort outside of regular teaching duties. When teachers have a heavy workload due to teaching responsibilities, lesson planning, grading, and other tasks, completing RPMS tools can become a burden that adds to their stress and workload. Teachers may also be responsible for other ancillary tasks, such as attending meetings, participating in extracurricular activities, and engaging with parents or guardians, which further adds to their workload and time constraints.

The challenge of completing RPMS tools with limited time, a heavy teaching workload, and ancillary tasks underscore the importance of designing performance evaluation systems that are streamlined and efficient, provide adequate support and resources for teachers, and allow them to focus on their primary responsibility of teaching and supporting student learning.

The participants shared that completing RPMS tools requires time and cannot be accomplished in one sitting, so they would use their weekends and holidays to answer the tools. They would even take the tools at home as there is not enough time to finish everything in school. The participants shared that they are already burdened with RPMS and find it stressful to accomplish the tasks, particularly the MOVs. The teachers shared that MOVs are challenging to achieve, and it also takes time to take photos and other proof of performance.

In the study of Torneo and Mojica (2019), the authors claimed that the performance management process in the Philippines is bureaucratic, highly administrative, and a mere burden for employees and managers. Similarly, the findings of the study coincide with the results of the survey by Dizon et al. (2018), where they found that the participants found the RPMS rating tool extra challenging because there were lots of hurdles in accomplishing and meeting the necessary outputs for every objective, in addition to daily tasks.

Under this theme, it was reiterated how RPMS compromises the time teachers should spend teaching. According to the interviews and discussions, teachers can only perform their teaching tasks if they are preoccupied with fulfilling their MOVs. The teachers shared that they are also having difficulty balancing their personal and professional lives as they are busy trying to complete the RPMS tools, apart from doing teaching-related tasks. For the participants, RPMS is an added workload and burden to teachers.

Understanding the concept of a Results-based Performance Management System and its indicators

Understanding the concept of RPMS and its indicators refers to gaining knowledge and comprehension of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) and the specific indicators used to evaluate teachers' performance. The indicators used in RPMS may vary depending on the context and goals of the evaluation. Still, they generally include categories such as teaching effectiveness, professional development, and contributions to the school community.

Understanding the concept of RPMS and its indicators is important for teachers, administrators, and other stakeholders in the educational system. It provides a framework for evaluating teacher performance and identifying areas for improvement. It also promotes a culture of continuous learning and professional development among teachers, which can positively impact student learning outcomes.

However, while the idea behind RPMS is good, teachers need help with its implementation. According to Cappelli and Tavis (2016), most performance management systems are more process-driven and are more concerned with performance appraisal (PA) instead of investigating PMS holistically. As determined from the data, one of the salient challenges of teachers is that the participants are having a hard time understanding the concept of RPMS and its indicators. Indeed, it can be hard to appreciate a system when you do not understand its basic concepts.

Apart from the challenge of hardly understanding RPMS, the participants also shared that they are even more challenged by it because they need guidance and support in completing the tool. There is also no feedback mechanism in place. Hence, the participants need to be sure if they are doing things right or if they submitted the right MOVs.

The challenge of understanding the core concepts of RPMS is compounded by the need to fulfill teaching and ancillary tasks. The participants shared that they are so preoccupied with understanding the lessons they are about to deliver that they no longer have time to digest or comprehend what RPMS is all about.

These findings relate to the study of Owino, Oluoch, and Kimemia (2019), which found that feedback and reward were the strongest predictors of employee productivity and that for PMS to succeed, there should be realistic and clear goals for the team, regular review discussions on the employees' performance, regular constructive feedback, and a reward system linked to the results of the appraisal, which should be just and fair.

Rating teachers

Another challenge identified by the study is rating teachers. The challenge of rating teachers refers to the difficulties faced by administrators or evaluators in assessing teachers' performance through the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) and dealing with their attitudes and perceptions towards the system.

Rating teachers through RPMS involves evaluating their teaching effectiveness, professional development, and contributions to the school community using specific indicators and criteria. This complex process requires objective and reliable data sources, consistent and fair evaluations, and effective communication with teachers about the evaluation process and outcomes. However, the attitudes and perceptions of teachers towards RPMS can also impact the evaluation process and create additional challenges. For example, some teachers may view RPMS as a burden that adds to their workload and stress levels. In contrast, others may need more clarification on

the indicators or criteria used for evaluation.

Some participants shared that they cannot rate appropriately because there is an unwritten mandate to provide high ratings to everyone. In that way, even if the raters would like to give an unsatisfactory score in the event of lacking MOVs, they cannot do so due to this informal order. Also, the raters shared that they can only do something if the teacher has MOV. In the end, they are bound to provide high scores to please the teachers and maintain the school's good rating.

These attitudes and perceptions can affect their engagement with the evaluation process, willingness to provide feedback, and overall buy-in to the system.

Rating Teachers' and their attitudes and perceptions towards Results-based Performance Management System

Most interviewees were School Heads, Master Teachers, and raters. According to them, RPMS is already challenging. However, the negative attitudes and perceptions of the teachers make it even harder for them to understand RPMS and complete its tools. For instance, teachers would only work on their MOVs during deadlines.

The teachers need to practice organizing their MOVs and files relevant to RPMS. According to Arumugham, Maelah, and Aman (2018), the success of RPMS largely depends on employee readiness, PMS objectives and direction, PMS measurements, and commitment from the management. The raters shared that if only the teachers were keen on keeping their files and MOVs, submitting on time and accomplishing the tools would be easier, implying that teachers need more time to be ready to achieve the tools. Another issue is the quality of MOVs.

As mentioned earlier, due to a lack of technical assistance and since there is a lack of knowledge and understanding on RPMS and how to accomplish it, the teachers tend to submit whatever they can get hold of or whatever they can copy from their co-teachers, thereby compromising the quality of the report.

Also, some participants shared that there are teachers who do not prioritize accomplishing RPMS due to their low appreciation of the system. With this lack of appreciation, they do not take RPMS seriously. They will even go to the length of getting ideas from social media or copying and pasting their co-teachers' responses.

Antagonistic environment due to Results-based Performance Management System

An antagonistic environment due to RPMS refers to a situation where the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) creates a hostile, adversarial, or confrontational atmosphere between teachers, administrators, or other stakeholders in the educational system. RPMS is designed to evaluate teachers' performance and promote accountability, transparency, and continuous improvement in teaching and learning. However, if the evaluation process is designed and implemented effectively, it can create an antagonistic environment that upholds teachers' and other stakeholders' trust, collaboration, and morale.

An antagonistic environment can also arise if the evaluation process is perceived as punitive or threatening rather than supportive or constructive. Teachers may feel they are being evaluated in a hostile or unsupportive manner, which can lead to defensiveness, resistance, or hostility toward the system.

The study of Modipane, Botha, and Blom (2018) found that their participants view PMS as unfair. The participants' negative perception of RPMS is compounded by the idea that RPMS is a burden to the teachers; thereby, accomplishing the tools becomes heavier for them. Some participants shared that RPMS becomes a leverage of School Heads against the teachers, and they are not even sure if the School Heads or the raters are rating them properly or if they are certain about what they are doing.

Cakir and Adiguzel (2020) emphasized the importance of role definition in preventing organizational conflict. Other participants shared that rater are too meticulous, while others ask for more than what is required in the tools. According to the participants, each rater interprets the objectives and indicators differently, making RPMS implementation even more complicated and difficult.

The results of this study are similar to that of Alshaikhi and Alshaikhi (2021). Alshaikhi and Alshaikhi (2021) found that teachers' perception of PMS was more inclined to dissatisfaction. This perception emanates from the problems encountered in the performance management process.

The participants also shared that the system does not represent the information needed to help managers make informed decisions and policies about the teachers. Other issues identified in the study were the lack of training for head teachers to conduct PMS effectively and the teachers' beliefs that there are bias errors in PMS implementation due to teachers' dissatisfaction.

Improvements Teachers Want About Results-based Performance Management System Implementation

After identifying the issues and challenges teachers encounter during RPMS completion, the participants identified recommendations and suitable actions to improve the implementation of RPMS in the Division and, possibly, within the Department of Education. T

he identified recommendations are presented in Table 3. From the significant statements, three themes were identified under this section: make RPMS more teacher-friendly, make RPMS easier to comply with, and provide reorientation and technical assistance.

Table 3. Recommended improvements in RPMS implementation

Case 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More time to complete RPMS • Put more emphasis on the importance of RPMS • Provide technical assistance to teachers and raters • Provide an expert or consultant to guide the teachers
Case 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper orientation
Case 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None
Case 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unambiguous and clear instructions
Case 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lessen requirements • Remove excessive and repetitive requirements • Electronic or paperless submission of requirements
Case 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodic or regular orientation and reorientation • Have a check list of required activities; MOVs if for added proof only • Lessen paper works of teachers • Paperless MOV • Make RPMS easier and less cumbersome for teachers
Case 7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revisit the implementation process • Conduct a refresher course on RPMS • Refresher course in a smaller group • Capacity building for teachers <hr/>

The significant statements of the cases are elaborated below:

Case 1 emphasized that although the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) faces challenges, it can be improved by allocating more time for teachers, highlighting its role in professional development, providing technical assistance, and having an expert guide. These measures streamline the process, making it more manageable and beneficial for educators.

Case 2 shared that implementing a Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) requires proper orientation, comprehensive programs, and ongoing support. This ensures teachers and raters understand the system's processes, objectives, and role in professional development. Providing ongoing refresher sessions maintains clarity and effectiveness.

Case 4 recommended clear and unambiguous instructions are crucial for improving the implementation of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). This reduces confusion and errors, enhances documentation quality, and improves the efficiency and effectiveness of the system.

Case 5 suggested that to improve the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS), requirements should be reduced. The department should also remove repetitive tasks and implement electronic submission. This will reduce administrative workload and improve efficiency, benefiting teachers and the educational system.

Case 6 shared that her recommendations for improving the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) include regular orientation sessions, simplifying documentation with a checklist, transitioning to a paperless MOV system, and ensuring teachers are well-informed. She also suggested revisiting the implementation process to identify areas for improvement, aiming to make the system more manageable and beneficial for all teachers.

Case 7 emphasized that refresher courses in smaller groups should improve the implementation of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). The department should also prioritize capacity-building initiatives and invest in ongoing training to empower educators and ensure smoother RPMS implementation.

From the cases, the following themes were generated:

Make RPMS more teacher-friendly

Making RPMS more teacher-friendly refers to improving the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) to make it more accessible, understandable, and supportive for teachers.

The majority of the participants shared that they find the RPMS implementation process difficult and challenging, to the point that it is not teacher-friendly, as it adds more stress and burden for them instead of making their lives easier.

This coincides with the findings of Dizon et al. (2018), stating that the RPMS rating tool was extra challenging because there were many hurdles in accomplishing and meeting the necessary outputs for every objective and daily task. One of the participants' suggestions is for the department to revisit the implementation process of RPMS. The participants recommended that RPMS be conducted at least once a year to ease the burden of preparing too many MOVs and paperwork. Some participants even recommended removing RPMS instead of changing its frequency or revisiting its implementation process.

One of the salient issues identified in the RPMS implementation is the unsuitability of some of its indicators, such as rating classrooms with IP learners when most classes still need IP learners. The participants recommended that RPMS be tailored according to the features of individual schools instead of having one-size-fits-all or generic tools concerning the distinct needs and features of schools.

These contrasts the recommendations of Negatu, Solomon, and Gideon (2017), who recommended that the organization set a general standard for performance appraisal to reduce biases and encourage employee participation in the evaluation process. While both recommendations are correct, a general standard for performance appraisal is only applicable if the variables are constant. However, for public schools in the Philippines with diverse conditions and features, the performance appraisal tools should be carefully considered to fit the various needs of schools.

The rating system is another point for RPMS to review. Some of the participants recommended that students be the raters instead of the School Head or Master Teachers because it is the students who have direct knowledge and experience of how their teachers perform.

The supervisors should only monitor the MOVs, but the students should ultimately rate their teachers. Another recommendation is to revise the rating system. According to the participants, the teachers' ratings should not affect the ratings of their immediate superiors. Further, RPMS should not be the sole basis for a teacher to be considered an Outstanding Teacher.

Make results-based performance management Systems easier to comply with.

Making RPMS easier to comply with refers to simplifying and streamlining the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) to reduce the burden and workload on teachers and other stakeholders involved in the evaluation process. Although some participants expressed that they understand the concept behind RPMS and what the system is for, most participants shared that RPMS is challenging to comply with as there are so many requirements and too much paperwork that some need to be more reasonable.

Similarly, Brown (2018) and his group suggested research that investigates the system's gaps to effectively manage employees in the future. The participants recommended simplifying RPMS and lessening its requirements.

According to Cakir and Adiguzel (2020), organizations have difficulty implementing performance management systems as some aspects are not considered. Carefully considering the implementation of RPMS will allow teachers to focus on teaching and make completing RPMS less stressful. One of the participants' issues is that RPMS requires bulky papers for printing and photocopying. Considering the limited resources, the teachers are compelled to shell out from their pockets to purchase bond paper and for printing. The recommendation to lessen paperwork and remove excessive and repetitive requirements emanates from the fact that the Department of Education issues too much paperwork and ancillary tasks that encumber public school teachers.

Regarding the recommendation to lessen paperwork, the participants also requested paperless processing and submission of MOVs. They shared that technology should be used to make RPMS submission easier, such as digitalizing the checking, submission, and rating process.

Reorientation and technical assistance

Reorientation for teachers refers to the process of updating or refreshing their knowledge and skills regarding RPMS. This may involve attending professional development workshops, seminars, or training sessions or engaging in self-directed learning activities. Furthermore, technical assistance for teachers refers to providing support and guidance to teachers regarding RPMS implementation.

The majority of the participants shared that they were not properly oriented or that the orientation happened only once, and no calibration or reorientation happened after. Thus, the participants recommended having a refresher course or regular reorientation to deepen their knowledge and to have the opportunity to clarify issues or ask questions.

In the same vein, the study of Kaupa and Atiku (2020) recommended that management provide training building to educate employees on the goals and benefits of PMS and enforce policies to ensure system compliance or another round of orientation is needed by those who were newly hired and have no idea what RPMS is all about. Calibration sessions will also be an opportunity to clarify the objectives of RPMS so that the teachers have a better appreciation of its rationale and importance to the teachers. The participants recommended that the reorientations or deepening sessions be in smaller groups for better concentration and less distraction.

Another recommendation of the participants is for the Division to provide more technical assistance and capacity-building to teachers. This way, the teachers will have an expert or a consultant to go to when they need clarification on some issues related to RPMS.

Also, having a technical expert or a center for technical assistance will eliminate the practice of resorting to YouTube or social media for ideas on RPMS completion. This will also eradicate or lessen the copying of responses among teachers.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

The secondary public school teachers under the Tacloban City Divisions have issues related to RPMS implementation. These issues emanate from a lack of knowledge and understanding of RPMS, issues related to RPMS tools, lack of technical assistance, and

excessive workloads that affect the teachers' time for teaching. In the end, the teachers view RPMS as an additional burden, and the system is ineffective in measuring the teachers' overall performance.

Also, the teachers of secondary public schools in Tacloban City are challenged to complete the RPMS tools, which they find stressful and difficult. The tools also affect their teaching time. The study also concludes that the teachers of Tacloban City Division find RPMS burdensome. The RPMS implementation is all the more challenged due to the teachers' negative attitudes and difficulty rating the teachers properly.

These findings corroborate the issues and challenges identified by previous studies on the RPMS mentioned in this study. By the teacher-participants' own admission, the current RPMS is ineffective in capturing their real school performance. Hence, the evaluation results from the RPMS are not a reliable measure of performance. At best, it is a tool, which they use to comply with a DepEd requirement and to get their incentives.

Furthermore, the RPMS implementation in Tacloban City Division requires improvements so that it can be better understood and appreciated by the teachers. This will result in a better quality of education and learning, which will benefit the learners and the Philippine educational system in general.

Lastly, the study concludes that completing the RPMS requires time from teachers that should have otherwise been used for preparation, teaching, and improving student learning outcomes.

The following specific recommendations can also be adopted to make the model a reality:

Provide Adequate Training. Teachers should receive comprehensive training on RPMS, including the assessment process, tools, and guidelines. This training should be ongoing and include updates on any changes to the system. Also, the raters should be capacitated so that the teachers and raters have a common understanding of RPMS.

The RPMS assessment process should also be simplified to make it easier for teachers to understand and complete. This will help ensure that teachers are not overwhelmed by the process and can focus on improving their performance. Simplifying the process would mean the Division alone should conduct orientations. The teachers should only be required to submit needed documents. Head Teachers/MTs or coordinators must collect MOVs immediately for banking purposes. For integrity, the papers must be marked "received" with a date and time. Schools must strategize how to collect MOVs more simply and easily.

the performance metrics used in RPMS should be clarified to ensure that teachers fully understand how they are being assessed. This will help teachers focus on the areas they need to improve and track their progress more effectively. Ratings should be given based on RPMS rubrics.

Another recommendation is that DepEd follow the RPMS cycle. During each RPMS cycle, there should be orientation, technical assistance, and feedback. Feedback should be provided to teachers in a timely manner. This will help teachers understand their strengths and weaknesses and take action to improve their performance. The Division office should closely monitor the TA. Monitor the school learning action plan (SLAC) to ensure RPMS is included in the topics.

Teachers should be encouraged to collaborate with their peers to share best practices and learn from one another. This will help build a culture of continuous improvement and support among teachers. There should be regular group or buddy tutoring. Technology should also be used to simplify the process and make it more accessible for teachers. This could include online resources, tools, and digital platforms for completing and submitting assessments.

The Department support the professional development of its teachers. Teachers should be provided with professional development opportunities to help them build the skills they need to improve their performance. These could include workshops, training sessions, and mentoring programs.

This study suggests adopting the improved RPMS model proposed in this study.

Finally, the researcher recommends that further studies be conducted to substantiate or deflate this study's findings.

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